

Extrusion coating as a tool for sustainable solid-state battery manufacturing

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1. Introduction

The traditional manufacturing processes of lithium-ion battery electrodes are notably energy-intensive and environmentally challenging. Primarily, these methods rely on the solvent N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), which is not only hazardous but also adds significant cost to production. The use of NMP requires extensive safety protocols, including labour protection and explosion prevention measures, while also demanding large spaces and high energy consumption for the solvent recovery and drying steps. Notably, the drying and solvent recovery processes alone can constitute up to 40% of the total energy consumption in lithium-ion battery cell production, contributing significantly to the carbon footprint of the manufacturing process (Lu et al., 2022).

Given these challenges, there is a compelling need for innovation in electrode manufacturing that circumvents the use of harmful solvents. Solvent-free, dry electrode production presents a promising alternative, drastically reducing the ecological footprint by eliminating the need for solvent recovery and reducing the energy demands of thermal drying. This method not only addresses environmental concerns but also reduces production costs and safety hazards associated with solvent use.

Recent advancements in dry coating technologies offer viable solutions. Notably, the Maxwell Process, reportedly being implemented in Tesla's Gigafactories, leverages such innovations. This method utilizes twin screw extrusion to finely control the mixing and fibrillation of binder materials like polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), which forms a stable matrix capable of supporting the electrochemical active and conductive particles within the electrode.

This solvent-free approach not only aligns with modern environmental and safety standards but also demonstrates improved battery performance in terms of rate capability and cycling stability. This is achieved by enhancing the microstructural properties of the cathode films, which are critical to the electrode's function and longevity. As the demand for lithium-ion batteries continues to surge, driven by the electric vehicle and renewable energy sectors, transitioning to solvent-free manufacturing processes becomes not just beneficial but essential for sustainable growth and innovation in battery technology.

Dry processing of cathodes for battery applications can take two distinct approaches depending on the type of battery. For lithium-ion batteries, which use a liquid electrolyte, the electrode structure must be porous to facilitate the diffusion of lithium ions. Conversely, for solid-state batteries that employ a polymer electrolyte, the electrode's pores should be completely filled with an ionically conductive polymer electrolyte (in this case, the binder polymer electrolyte) to enable lithium ions diffusion in the absence of a liquid electrolyte. Our goal is to develop these zero-void electrodes, optimizing ion transport across different battery technologies.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Our choice for the cathode active material was NMC811, *i.e.*, lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide with a ratio of nickel/manganese/cobalt of 8:1:1. The high nickel content will allow high energy density and minimises also the use of cobalt, which is considered as a challenging raw material as part of it is mined in unethical or environmentally harmful conditions.

A commercially available polymer electrolyte material, either polypropylene carbonate (PPC) or polyethylene carbonate (PEC), was used as the electrolyte and the binder. They were acquired from Empower Materials. Carbon black powder, C65 from Imerys, was used as the conducting additive, and high purity (99.9%) Lithium difluoro(oxalato)borate (LiDFOB) from MSE Supplies as the Li-salt.

2.2 Extrusion coating

In this work we made different compositions of NMC811, PPC/PEC, conductive carbon and a lithium salt using a twin-screw extruder.

The materials were accurately weighed and pre-mixed using a SpeedMixer® DAC 150 (Hauschild GmbH, Hamm, Germany) at 2500 rpm for 30 seconds. The weighing and premixing of materials were carried out in a glove box due to the hygroscopic nature of the lithium salt. This was followed by melt-blending using a DSM Xplore mini-scale twin-screw extruder (Xplore Instruments BV, Sittard, The Netherlands) with temperatures ranging from 130°C to 230°C, screw speed set at 100 rpm, and a mixing time of 4 minutes. After melt-blending in the micro-compounder, the compounds were transferred in a molten state to a Thermo-Haake minijet injection moulding machine (Thermo Fisher Scientific™, Massachusetts, USA) to prepare flat specimens, each approximately sized at 25×25×2 mm³. Injection parameters included an injection temperature relevant to the micro-compounder temperature, a mould temperature of 40°C, injection time of 10 seconds, pressure set at 1000 bar, and a hold time of 5 seconds. The injection moulded polymer samples were later cut into smaller pieces before the hot-pressing step.

The hot-pressing process for samples involves placing the compound between PTFE films and subjecting them to specific temperatures (120°C and 140°C when PEC and PPC are in the compound accordingly) for melting and flattening of the material by a pressing equipment (MKH PRESS, Jämsänkoski, Finland). Following the pressing, the elements are allowed to cool down, and the PTFE films are removed, leaving behind flat sheets. These sheets are then hot-pressed onto aluminium films with different primer layers, ensuring secure bonding between the polymer sheets and the aluminium substrate. This second hot-pressing step is conducted on just one side of the aluminium films, preserving their structural integrity while increasing the overall adhesion and compatibility of the composite materials.

Investigated parameters were:

1. Type of the polymer electrolyte and its effect on the extrusion process.
2. Active material (AM) / polymer ratio in the composite aiming to maximize AM content while maintaining the extrudability of the composite.
3. Hot pressing the extruded pellets to adjust the AM loading with minimum voids to allow ionic diffusion in solid electrolyte.
4. Effect of primers on the performance.

Figure 1. Twin-screw extruder for laboratory scale tests.

2.3 Electrochemical and structural characterization

The electrochemical performance of the extrusion processed and hot pressed positive electrodes was tested in CR2016 Hohsen coin cells with a 750 μm thick metallic lithium (acquired from Alfa Aesar) as the negative electrode and a liquid electrolyte (LiPF₆ in ethylene carbonate (EC) / dimethyl carbonate (DMC), EC:DMC 1:1, from Elyte), using a glass fibre separator (GF/A, Whatman). A 15 μm thick aluminium foil was used as the current collector as such and as coated with a primer from Armor Battery Films.

The investigation of the vertical (cross-sectional) morphology of the electrodes involved a multi-step approach. At the first step, the electrode samples were cut to the appropriate size (approx. 0.5×0.5 cm²) and exposed to Ar broad ion beam (BIB) milling (acc. voltage: 4 kV, exposure time: 120 min, T = 23 °C) using JEOL IB-19520CCP Cryo Cross Section Polisher. Subsequently, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was utilized to acquire cross-sectional images of the polished electrode samples employing JEOL JIB-4700 instrument operating at acc. voltage of 5 – 10 kV.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Extrusion coating

The first extrusion tests were done with the two different polymer electrolytes. The goal was to identify if it is possible to reach optimal (low enough) viscosity, and thus reasonable force, during extrusion. This was done in several different temperatures. Even though temperatures above 200°C would show lowest viscosity and the extrusion process would be easier to perform, it is not possible to use such high temperatures as the lithium salt might not be thermally stable anymore. It is thus important to find a polymer, which has suitable viscosity and processability at lower temperatures. In addition, the mixing of the polymer and the other components need to be evaluated. Figure 2 shows the force required for the extrusion process for both polymers in different temperatures. Both show similar viscosity trends. However, mixing and handling of PPC was easier compared to PEC. Thus, we chose PPC as the polymer electrolyte for further tests.

It was possible to process the blend of PPC, NMC811, carbon black and the Li-salt in the twin-screw extruder. Figure 3 shows the samples after the extrusion process and injection moulding steps, after which the layers were hot pressed on the current collector as thin electrode films. It is noticeable that there was no need for an additional binder, such as commonly used fluorinated polymers, as the polymer electrolyte itself holds the particles together and attached on the current collector.

Force Vs. time for PPC and PEC at different processing temperatures during 4 mins

Figure 2. Required force in the extrusion test, using different temperatures and both polymer electrolytes (PPC and PEC).

Figure 3. Picture of the extrusion processed and injection moulded cathode composite samples before hot pressing.

3.2 Electrochemical characterization

Extruded composites were attached to current collector foils to be used in battery tests. Electrochemical results revealed that using a current collector with primer has better rate performance due to higher electrical conductivity.

Two series of extruded samples on the current collector (with primer) underwent different hot press conditions. Using liquid electrolyte in the half-cells, electrochemical results showed that samples with low pressure (voids were detected by SEM cross-section, see Figure 4) were functioning at room temperature while samples which were pressed harder (low void) required higher temperature for rate capability tests. These cells (6 repeats) were all stopped at room temperature due to high overpotentials and after increasing temperature to 40 °C, the overpotential decreased and they performed well (high temperature capacity-voltage plot is shown in Figure 5).

Figure 4. Cross-section SEM images from the extrusion processed cathode composite layers, composing of NMC811, carbon black and the PPC polymer electrolyte. Both smaller and larger voids can be seen. However, it is not clear if the largest voids are just due to sample preparation.

Figure 5. Capacity-voltage plot for a coin cell at 40 degrees, using NMC811 cathode composite electrode (mixed with PPC polymer electrolyte, LiDFOB salt, and carbon black, hot pressed under high pressure), liquid electrolyte and Li metal anode.

It is common that polymer electrolytes require elevated temperatures for reaching reasonable ionic conductivity. This is also true for the polymers tested in this study. Thus, the fact that the cells processed using high pressure did not work at room temperature indicates that there were no or only little voids. Otherwise, the liquid electrolyte would have filled in these voids, and the cells would have been functional. On the other hand, as these cells worked at 40 degrees, it shows that the polymer electrolyte was mixed well with the other materials, and it could function as the platform for the ions to move.

As the porosity could be adjusted by the hot-pressing parameters, it shows the potential of the extrusion coating method for battery manufacturing. It is possible to prepare electrodes both for cells that are using a liquid electrolyte and cells that have a binder solid polymer electrolyte in the cathode composite layer. So far, we have tested the electrodes still with the liquid electrolyte, but the next step is to also change the separator and the liquid electrolyte to a separator solid polymer electrolyte, resulting in a solid-state cell. Also, polymer electrolytes with room temperature operation are under development.

3.3 Addressing sustainability aspects of SSBs

Building on our previous results and discussions, we now focus on how solid-state batteries, particularly those employing lithium metal electrodes, offer a transformative approach from a sustainability perspective. Using lithium metal negative electrodes offers several potential advantages over conventional lithium-ion batteries. These include a higher specific energy density, a chemistry that is more environmentally friendly, and the elimination of the need for a copper current collector, thereby reducing the amount of inactive cell material. The conventional methods, heavily reliant on the hazardous solvent NMP, not only consume a significant amount of energy but also pose substantial environmental risks. This scenario compels us to seek innovative approaches in electrode manufacturing that mitigate both ecological and safety hazards. Moreover, employing lithium metal electrodes opens up the possibility of utilizing positive electrode materials that do not contain lithium, which can enhance battery aging and minimize lithium losses during long term cycling. (Berg et al. 2018).

For example, Vandepaer et al. (2017) present a comparative study of lithium metal polymer (LMP) and lithium-ion stationary batteries. In this study context lithium-ion batteries have higher environmental impacts in terms of global warming and human health damage, due to their aluminum sourced from China, which relies on coal-generated power, whereas LMP batteries use aluminum from Quebec produced with hydropower, resulting in 14% less damage in the human health category and 24% less damage in the climate change category compared to LIB. Nevertheless, LMPs have more significant environmental impacts than LIBs in other key areas, including aquatic eutrophication, land occupation,

ionizing radiation, and aquatic ecotoxicity. This disparity is primarily due to increased blasting for gold extraction required for LMP batteries, driven by the demand for integrated circuits.

Another example comes from Wu et al. (2018), who explore the environmental impact of next-generation lithium-ion batteries by comparing lithium metal and silicon nanowire anodes to traditional graphite ones. Their primary goal is to comprehensively analyze the life cycle of batteries with different negative electrodes. They find that the Global Warming Potential (GWP) resulting from 1 kg of NCM lithium metal anode cells is 21.12 kg CO₂-eq. It is also observed that batteries with lithium metal anodes have a significantly lower environmental footprint than those with graphite. This underscores the potential of adopting lithium metal to mitigate environmental impacts throughout the battery life cycle. Lithium metal anode with its high specific capacity, lightweight nature, and environmental benefits, emerged as a promising candidate for future traction batteries.

The use of low-cost raw materials for synthesizing solid electrolytes can contribute to the development of safer and more reliable next-generation batteries (Wang et al., 2020). These benefits contribute to lower cell costs, reduced climate impact, decreased abiotic depletion potential, and lower toxicity compared to lithium-ion batteries with similar designs. In respect to the manufacturing, the advantages conferred by roll-to-roll (R2R) processes for sustainability in lithium metal battery production extend beyond mere operational efficiencies, addressing key facets such as resource utilization, energy efficiency, and environmental impact. By enabling high throughput and reducing waste through continuous operation, R2R methodologies optimize resource utilization while minimizing material wastage. Moreover, the inherent energy efficiency of R2R processes, when coupled with innovative machine design strategies, not only reduces operational costs but also aligns with broader sustainability objectives by curbing energy consumption.

Expanding on the environmental impacts highlighted in the comparative analysis of Li-ion and LMP batteries, the application of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) emerges as a crucial method for evaluating these effects comprehensively. Therefore, one of the primary challenges is the need to extend the system boundary of LCSA from a micro to macro level analysis, dealing with complex dynamic relationships between social, economic, and environmental indicators, and integrating more quantitative social indicators (Onat et al., 2017). Additionally, there is a need to address uncertainties and develop scenario-based decision support tools for multi-criteria decision making (Onat et al., 2017). Furthermore, the difficulties of integrating the interrelationships between the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of LCSA results in decision-making pose a significant challenge (Hannouf & Assefa, 2018). The challenges also encompass the consistent execution of the three life cycle-based assessment methods, the relatively low maturity of Social Life Cycle Assessment, and the adequate presentation and interpretation of results (Tarne et al., 2017). Moreover, practical challenges in the operationalization of LCSA and integrated LCSA include defining coherent system boundaries, conducting sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, addressing rebound effects, trade-offs, and biased decision-making between social, economic, and environmental aspects (Zeug et al., 2021). The challenges also extend to the need for more practical examples of LCSA, efficient ways of communicating LCSA results, and the requirement for more data and methods, particularly for social indicators (Lin et al., 2020), and comprehensive uncertainty assessment (Guinée, 2016).

In light of these complexities, effectively leveraging Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) in the context of battery technology requires not only expanding the scope and precision of our assessments but also improving the integration and communication of the results to support more informed and balanced sustainability decisions across environmental, economic, and social dimensions.

4. Conclusions

Our study and examples from literature and industry clearly show that dry coating methods can increase the sustainability of battery processing. In addition, solid-state batteries bring additional positive impacts towards more sustainable batteries. However, dry coating is still rarely used in industry and research is needed to bring such methods into higher readiness level. Combining knowhow from different industries will be a key to tackle the upscaling challenges in a short time. In addition, accessible pilot lines to bring the ideas from lab to larger scale are needed. We do not have time to waste, as batteries will be needed in large amounts to reach the climate neutrality targets. For example, The International Energy Agency

(IEA) has reported that the electric vehicle battery deployment increased by 40% in 2023, with 14 million new electric cars (IEA, 2024). And the battery demand is growing rapidly, every year, both for EVs and for stationary energy storage markets.

The increasing need for batteries highlights the importance of making sure that their processing is sustainable and the greenhouse gas emissions from battery manufacturing are minimised. This is stated also in the European Batteries Regulation (EU, 2023). It is notable that the emissions from battery manufacturing need to be reported for each battery soon – starting from electric vehicle batteries, which need to contain information about their carbon footprint already in 2025. Dry extrusion coating is one of the key tools for reaching energy/cost efficiency and decreased emissions. In addition, it will enable also better performance and energy density for batteries as it is possible to prepare thicker electrodes with high quality. Thus, we see a lot of potential for this processing method.

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